

GENERATION, MODELLING AND VALIDATION OF STATISTICALLY EQUIVALENT MICRO-STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Processing properties of fibrous reinforcements and mechanical properties of composites are strongly influenced by reinforcement heterogeneity at the micro-scale. Disregarding the random arrangement of filaments at the micro-scale can lead to an overestimation of mechanical properties [1]. The random arrangement can result in unpredicted micro-crack formation within a component, which in turn reduces the service life of a part [2]. Most models incorporating micro-scale variability of the filament arrangement are based on artificially generated random configurations [3]. Owing to the difficulty in gathering data on the intrinsic variability of fibre reinforcements [4], algorithms generating statistically equivalent micro-structures are rarely implemented. This study describes an automated method for the determination of parameters to describe the micro-structure of a fibre bundle and statistical analysis of the measurement data. In addition, an algorithm is proposed to generate equivalent representative micro-structure models adapted from the work of Vaughan and McCarthy [5]. These models can then be used to predict reinforcement processing properties, e.g. resin flow during impregnation in composites processing, and micro-scale properties of composite parts.

2 Materials and Processing

2.1 Sample Manufacture

To characterise the degree of heterogeneity in fibre bundles at different compression levels, single layer composite sheets were moulded and cured at different cavity heights, effectively varying the fibre volume fraction, V_f . Panels with dimensions 125 mm × 60 mm were made from “non-crimp” carbon fibre

fabric and a low viscosity epoxy resin system. The fabric consisted of yarns with a 12K filament count, stabilized by thin glass weft yarns coated with a thermoplastic polymer. The specimens were moulded by circumferential injection of the liquid resin into a stiff metallic tool containing the fabric. The mould cavity height, h , i.e. the level of fabric compression, was varied. Three sets of samples with V_f of 0.45, 0.60 and 0.74 were produced using a mould with cavity height of 0.37 mm, 0.28 mm and 0.22 mm, respectively. Depending on V_f , the injection pressures used were between 1 bar and 4 bar to ensure complete mould filling. The resin was preheated to 70 °C before the injection pressure was applied. Subsequently, the temperature was increased to 130 °C to achieve the required low resin viscosity and to initiate the curing process. During injection, the resin viscosity, μ_f , was estimated to be approximately 0.025 Pa·s.

2.2 Experimental Methodology

Moulded and cured specimens were analysed by means of optical microscopy. This allowed the micro-structure to be determined at a high resolution. Other imaging techniques, such as micro-Computed Tomography [6], were identified to have inferior resolution. Images were acquired with a brightfield reflected light microscope equipped with an automated stage and a 12 bit monochrome camera. The pixel spacing, i.e. pixel centre to pixel centre distance of the resulting images, was determined to be 0.093 μm . Large area scanning was enabled by a computer controlled stage, which allows automated x - y positioning as well as automated z -positioning of the sample. Stitching of overlapping single images enables larger areas to be studied [7-9]. A stitching code was implemented based on Fast-Fourier correlations [10] programmed

in Matlab[®]. Micrographic analysis of cross-sections of the moulded and cured specimens allowed the filament distribution to be identified (Fig. 1). Images were analysed automatically at much higher resolution compared to examples reported in the literature [11].

Fig. 1. Cross-sections of composite specimens produced by resin transfer moulding at a gauge pressure of $p = 4$ bar and varying cavity heights, h . A) $h = 0.37$ mm, B) $h = 0.28$ mm and C) $h = 0.22$ mm. Carbon fibre bundle with 12K filament count; dry spots appear black.

3 Image Analysis

The theoretical resolution of an optical light microscope is limited by the wavelength of the light used [12] and can be determined as about half the wavelength [13]. For visible light, the maximum achievable resolution is therefore about $0.2 \mu\text{m}$. It should be noted, however, that several techniques were developed in recent years which enable resolutions approaching 20 nm [14]. The resolution limit of $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ means that it is impossible for edges of touching fibres to be clearly distinguished.

To gain morphological data from the acquired images, a simple colour thresholding technique is often employed [7, 15]. Inevitable differences in lighting, local light reflections and shading [12] makes it unfeasible to use a single global threshold for a complete image which can easily contain up to 250 individual fibres. This effect is amplified locally by the presence or absence of filament cross-sections within the image. This will therefore result in different greyscale values for the same object. Furthermore, rounding effects of the specimen at the sample edges due to polishing of the specimen leads to fibres in the images appearing darker with less pronounced boundaries. Their greyscale values will therefore be lower than in regions of fibre

agglomeration. An automated image analysis process was developed, based on the edge detection of local colour gradients, to overcome these issues.

3.1 Image Processing

Since the simple thresholding technique cannot be applied for accurate detection of filament cross-sections, a different approach is utilised here, based on prior knowledge of the expected filament shape. In a first step, areas of interest within the image are determined. The contrast of the bright and dark areas, fibres and matrix respectively, is enhanced in the image. This is followed by a simple global threshold of the entire image and a watershed separation [16] of the remaining objects. Even though it is not possible to extract precise data from every single fibre cross-section, it is possible to determine centre points for specific areas of interest. These points are used as an input for a first approximation of the fibre cross-section centres. A window of defined size is centred on every single position, and localised image analysis is executed.

It is possible to detect fibre edges directly in these local images. A widely used and generally accepted method of edge detection was developed by Canny [17]. This algorithm detects edges by examining neighbourhoods of pixels and evaluates the gradients. If this algorithm is applied to the image of a fibre, it can be demonstrated that the detected fibre radii are underestimated (Fig. 2). The minor ellipse axis, representing the actual fibre diameter, is significantly under predicted ($6.48 \mu\text{m}$ instead of $7.17 \mu\text{m}$ here). Compared to a set of 29 reference measurements of manually fitted ellipses on high magnification Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images, it can be shown that the major ellipse axis is underestimated by 1.9% and the minor ellipse axis by 8.4%. This shows that the direct edge fitting approach is not applicable for the obtained micrographs.

Fig. 2. A) Edges detected with Canny algorithm, B) manually fitted ellipse on SEM image.

Instead of using the original image, local colour gradients can be calculated (Fig. 3A). The calculation of colour gradients in these locally confined areas also allows absolute colour values of the image to be neglected. The problem of different levels of contrast or brightness, which depends on the position of the fibre in the overall image, can therefore be overcome. After smoothing the gradient image, the edges can be determined using Canny's edge detector. The image of the fibre boundary gradients will show two distinct edges (Fig. 3B). The inner edge (yellow dots) is present because the gradient of a fibre edge exhibits a greyscale gradient in two directions. The points belonging to the inner edge can be eliminated using a stencil based on a fitted ellipse through the initially determined Canny edges (Fig. 2A). This leaves just the outer fibre edge of interest and the edges detected from neighbouring fibre cross-sections as noise.

Fig. 3. A) Representation of colour gradients of a fibre with parts of touching fibres. B) Detected Canny edges of the fibre (black *) and Canny edges of the gradients (white and yellow dots). Canny edges marked yellow are removed.

In order to remove all points not belonging to the actual fibre edge, the distance to the image centre is calculated for all points. Only the points closest to

the centre for every 5 degrees are selected, and an ellipse is fitted through these remaining points (Fig. 4A). Since it cannot be ensured that all points from adjacent fibre borders are removed, the fitted ellipse is used as a new stencil. A selected offset is applied to the ellipse and any outliers removed iteratively and the ellipse is refitted through the remaining points. The optimal detection of the actual filament boundary was found using a 2 pixel offset. The obtained fit is shown in Fig. 4B. The resulting differences between the major and minor ellipse axes compared to the manual ellipse fit shown in Fig. 2B are 1.6 % and 0.5 %. The good fit of the minor ellipse axis enables the precise estimation of the fibre diameter distribution within a complete fibre bundle.

Fig. 4. A) Initial ellipse fit of fibre boundary based on the determination of colour gradients. Noise, points belonging to edges of touching fibres are present. B) Final result of the fitted ellipse to the fibre boundary after iteratively removing points outside the first ellipse fit.

Compared to a set of manually fitted ellipses (Fig. 2B), an average underestimation of 0.8 % of the minor ellipse axis was identified. The measurement of 300,000 single filament cross-sections showed a normal distribution of the filament diameter with a mean of $6.97 \mu\text{m}$ and a standard deviation of $0.39 \mu\text{m}$, which is in good agreement with the nominal values. The precision of these results is superior to measurement data reported in the literature [5, 18, 19].

The developed procedure for image processing implemented in Matlab[®] allows the automated analysis of filaments within complete fibre bundles. Problems encountered during conventional image analysis employing simple techniques such as colour thresholding are overcome with the proposed method by analysing colour gradients instead.

Fitting a predefined shape to the filament edges allowed the precise determination of filament dimensions. The presumed elliptical fit of the filament boundary may be questionable for the cross-sections of other filaments, e.g. natural fibres, and Kratmann et al. [20] pointed out that this method is sensitive to irregular shapes. However, the proposed process allows the use of any other shape approximation. This makes the proposed technique a powerful tool to systematically analyse large areas within a composite at high magnification in an automated manner.

4 Results

4.1 Bundle Shape

A method to accurately determine the filament dimensions was described in Section 3.1. Based on this information and the exact location of the filaments, it is possible to deduce the edge of the entire fibre bundle. The width of individual bundles, w , initially increases with a decrease in h (Fig. 1A and B). Due to the increase in w , adjacent bundles overlap for $h = 0.28$ mm (Fig. 1B) and merge for $h = 0.23$ mm (Fig. 1C). Only in areas where the fixation thread is present, the yarn remains physically separated (Fig. 1C; near left and right edge of image).

The global V_f in the mould cavity with height, h , can be estimated when the fabric areal density, A_f , the density of the material, ρ , and the number of layers, l , are known (1).

$$V_f = \frac{l \cdot A_f}{h \cdot \rho} \quad (1)$$

While V_f is inversely proportional to the cavity height, the change in bundle width with increasing compaction exhibits a non-linear relationship (Fig. 5). The width of the fibre bundle increases significantly in the initial stages of bundle compression. This suggests that the increase in global V_f from 0.45 to approximately 0.60 is coupled with a significant change of the fibre bundle shape in the textile layer as illustrated in Fig. 1. The internal V_f of the fibre bundle should therefore be less affected. Only if the bundle is further compressed (from 0.60 to 0.74 global V_f), the V_f within the

bundle should significantly increase because the overall change in bundle width is minimal. The inter-yarn space as seen in Fig. 1A is completely occupied when the bundle is highly compressed (Fig. 1C), and the increase in global V_f can only be achieved by a reordering of the filaments within the fibre bundle and not by bundle widening.

Fig. 5. Fibre bundle height, h , and width, w , as a function of the global fibre volume fraction, V_f . The error bars show the standard deviation of the measurements.

4.2 Micro-Structure

4.2.1 Nearest Neighbour Distances

Different statistical descriptors can be employed to describe the random arrangement of filaments within a fibre bundle [21, 22]. The distance of a filament to its n -th nearest neighbour can give an idea of the spatial arrangement of the filaments [23]. The mean distances for the first ten nearest neighbours, measured between the centre points of the filaments, are given for three V_f in Fig. 6. The graph clearly shows that the average inter-filament distance decreases with increasing levels of compaction. For $n = 1$, the closest neighbouring filament, the distance converges to the average filament diameter since the nearest possible distance is achieved when neighbouring filaments are in contact with each other. Furthermore, the decrease in inter-filament distance is more pronounced when the fibre bundle is compacted from 0.60 to 0.74 global V_f within the mould. This indicates that, due to a change in yarn shape (Section 4.1), inter-filament distances decrease less significantly when compacted from 0.45 to 0.60 global V_f .

Fig. 6. Mean filament distance to first to tenth nearest neighbour for three samples with $V_f = 0.45, 0.60$ and 0.74 . For comparison, the mean filament distances for a hexagonal (hex) arrangement are shown.

At the maximum packing density in perfectly hexagonal packing of identical filaments, the neighbouring distances for the first six neighbours, $n = 1$ to 6 , are identical at a value of the filament diameter, d . The filament distances for the neighbouring filaments $n = 7$ to 12 are at a value of $d \cdot \sqrt{3}$ and for $n = 13$ to 18 at a value of $2 \cdot d$ etc. With increasing levels of bundle compression, the average distance as a function of n converges to this step function, implying that a reduction in inter-filament spacing and increasing packing density are directly related to increasingly uniform filament distributions. This agrees with observations by Potluri and Sagar [24], who report flattening of fibre bundles by micro-scale filament reordering as a fabric compression mechanism.

4.2.2 Nearest Neighbour Angles

The distance to the n -th nearest neighbour (Fig. 6) indicates that with an increase in compaction of the fibre bundle, the inter-filament distance converges to the hexagonal closest packing. The angle, under which the n -th nearest neighbouring filament is located, should also reflect this increased degree of order within the fibre bundle and is often disregarded. For analysis of the samples, the 0° direction was chosen to be aligned with the width of the fibre bundle and hence, $\pm 90^\circ$ represents the direction of the sample thickness.

Fig. 7. Angle distributions for the location of the first (red), second to fourth (shades of grey) nearest neighbours. A) global $V_f = 0.45$ with no bundle compaction; B) global $V_f = 0.60$; C) global $V_f = 0.74$.

It can be demonstrated that the distribution of angles, under which the n -th nearest neighbours are located, changes significantly with increasing fabric compaction. With minimal fabric compaction, the distribution of angles is almost isotropic (Fig. 7A). A minor preference of the closest neighbour in direction of the bundle width ($0^\circ / 180^\circ$) can be observed. This could stem from the fabric production process when the fibre tow is flattened by pulling through various loops before being processed into the textile reinforcement and/or the fabric storage in the form of a tightly wound bobbin. The angle distributions become, however, less uniform with increasing compaction (Fig. 7B and C), i.e. increasing degree of order in the filament arrangement.

With an increase in compaction of the fibre bundle, the probability for the closest filament to be found in the compaction direction ($\pm 90^\circ$) is significantly increased (Fig. 7B). During the reduction in cavity height, the filament arrangement is compressed as a result of the compaction force. Filaments are pressed against each other in the compaction direction, reflected in the increased probability of finding the closest neighbour in the $\pm 90^\circ$ direction. The effect of yarn widening can also be observed from this data. Filaments are pushed in the direction normal to the compaction force. An increased probability of the third and fourth nearest neighbour to be located in the direction of the bundle width results. If the cavity height is further decreased, filaments in vertical contact (in bundle thickness direction) move normally to the compaction direction due to the reduced available space. Since the filament arrangement is already rather closely packed, further increase in bundle width is limited (Fig. 1). Hence, the filament arrangement is compacted more and approaches hexagonal close packing (Fig. 7C). An increased probability for a filament's n -th neighbour to be located at angles of 0° , 60° , 120° , 180° , 240° and 300° can be observed.

Misalignment of the angle distributions with respect to the direction of the bundle width and height can be observed. This effect is more distinct in the measured angle distribution of the sample with maximum compaction (Fig. 7C). The most probable location of the first neighbouring filament is at an angle of 120° or 300° respectively. It is assumed that

the onset of this preference of the angles results from the mould closing process. A slight misalignment of the upper and lower mould tool would lead to slightly misaligned compaction planes. This effect could be further pronounced when physically compacting the fibre reinforcement in the mould. An increased compaction force could have been introduced from one side of the mould, which would explain the preference for a certain angle for the (first) nearest neighbour position in Fig. 7.

5 Micro-Structure Generation

For modelling of micro-structural properties, i.e. reconstruction of filament arrangements at the micro-scale, several models have been proposed in the literature. The most simple method of generating random filament arrangements places non-overlapping disks with constant [25, 26] or varying [27] fibre radii randomly within a specified domain. A limitation to this method is the jamming limit at around $V_f = 0.55$ [28, 29], which is at the lower end of the typical local V_f within fibre bundles used in composite materials. Other studies induce randomness by disturbing regular [30] or random arrangements in defined ways [31, 32]. Varying numbers of stirring iterations can be employed to achieve different degrees of order [33]. Employing these techniques, artificial filament arrangements with V_f up to the theoretical maximum packing can be generated. However, each of these modelling approaches lacks a direct correlation to measured data to generate the micro-structure. This limitation is overcome by the modelling approach proposed by Vaughan and McCarthy [5], which uses measured distributions.

5.1 Reconstruction of Filament Arrangements

Statistically equivalent two-dimensional micro-structures were generated following an adapted version of the procedure described by Vaughan and McCarthy [5] by means of measured distributions of distances between neighbouring filaments. In their model, a pre-determined number of filaments are placed at given distances, which are picked randomly from measured distributions, and in random directions relative to a randomly placed starting filament. After the last filament is placed, the starting point is set to the first newly placed

filament, and the process is repeated. These steps are repeated until the specified domain is filled with filaments, and no additional filament can be placed.

The proposed algorithm was further developed to utilise the measurement data presented in Section 4.2. The adjustment of the nearest neighbour distributions to avoid double counts of distances between filaments which are each others' n -th nearest neighbour was omitted. This adjustment would effectively lead to a widening of the measured distributions. Allowing double counts does, however, reflect the reality where two filaments within one yarn cross-section can be each others' n -th nearest neighbour. To accommodate the change in procedure, the first four nearest neighbour distributions were used for the filament placement procedure.

For periodic hexagonal packing, the maximum $V_f = 0.91$ is achieved if the nearest neighbour distance is equal to the constant filament diameter. An identical nearest neighbour distance is found in the case of a square arrangement exhibiting maximum $V_f = 0.79$ for the first four nearest neighbours. It can be demonstrated, however, that the procedure described by Vaughan and McCarthy has a natural jamming limit of $V_f \sim 0.70$ if these neighbour distances are used in the reconstruction for the filament arrangement. This limit can be explained by the fact that, whilst the neighbouring filament distance is picked from a measured distribution, the neighbouring filament angle is randomly assigned. This introduces an unintended assumption about the arrangement which does not necessarily reflect the actual filament configuration (Fig. 8A). As indicated in Fig. 6, the filament distances seem to converge to the hexagonal arrangement when the fibre bundle is compacted. This compaction introduces some regularity which is also reflected in the neighbour angle distribution (Fig. 7). Therefore, it is necessary to take the actual angle distributions into account at which the n -th nearest filament is located most probably rather than using a randomly assigned angle. Incorporating this consideration into the procedure proposed by Vaughan and McCarthy, a statistically equivalent filament arrangement can be generated. By utilising the filament distance and angle distributions for periodic hexagonal packing with maximum $V_f = 0.91$ as previously, the actual

filament arrangement can be reconstructed (Fig. 8B). The jamming limit of the fibre placement algorithm as shown in Fig. 8A can be overcome. Depending on the provided input data, it is now possible to generate models at any achievable V_f .

Fig. 8. A) Reconstructed random filament arrangement ($V_f \sim 0.70$) following the procedure described by Vaughan and McCarthy [5] with neighbour distance distribution employed equal to the filament diameter. B) Filament arrangement ($V_f = 0.91$) achieved after additionally incorporating the angle distribution of a hexagonal configuration in the adapted model generator.

5.2 Validation of Generated Arrangements

The generated micro-structural models are validated with the same statistical descriptors as employed earlier, reflecting the orthotropy resulting from the bundle compaction. The generated V_f distribution for the micro-structure is similar to the distribution measured on cross-sectional samples of fibre bundles. In the case of a global V_f of 0.60, the average V_f within the fibre bundle was estimated as $V_f = 0.67 \pm 0.07$ whereas the reconstructed V_f was determined to be $V_f = 0.66 \pm 0.01$ over a large number of realisations. The mean V_f is slightly lower than the measured data and the distribution is more narrow. This narrow distribution is also clearly visible in the neighbour distribution data (Fig. 9). The measured neighbour distances are well within the confidence interval of one (log-normal) standard deviation.

Fig. 9. Measured n -th nearest neighbour distances (black x) of generated RVEs with $V_f = 0.66$ compared to the distributions mean (red diamond). The log-normal standard deviation is marked as gray shaded area.

6 Concluding Remarks

This study proposes a new method to quantify and describe the filament arrangement within fibre bundles of reinforcement fabrics for composites on the micro-scale. Single layer uni-directional carbon fibre reinforcements (12K filament count) were moulded at different cavity heights, effectively varying the V_f of the resulting samples. The moulded and cured specimens were analysed by means of micrographs of polished cross-sections. This allowed the micro-structure to be determined over a large area and at a high resolution. The developed method of automated analysis of stitched images in Matlab® allows the analysis of much higher resolution images compared to examples reported in the literature. This enables the systematic analysis of a large number of samples. To gain morphological data from the acquired images, an automated image analysis process was developed based on the edge detection of local colour gradients. This method overcomes issues commonly found when employing simple image thresholding. The detected filament outlines are approximated with an ellipse. With the automated detection method, the analysis time is relatively small and, for the case of carbon fibres, the shape assumption was concluded to be a good fit.

Compared to a set of manually fitted ellipses, an average underestimation of the minor ellipse axis of 0.8 % could be identified. The measurement of a large number of single filament cross-sections showed a normal distribution of the filament diameter which is in good agreement with the nominal values. It was concluded that the developed automated measurement technique for systematic analysis of micrographic cross-sections delivers superior results compared to measurement data previously presented in the literature. Different statistical descriptors can be employed for the random arrangement of filaments within a fibre bundle. The distance of a filament to its n -th nearest neighbour was selected to describe the spatial arrangement of the filaments. It was shown that these distances to nearest neighbours decrease with increasing fibre bundle compaction. In the literature, the increasing degree of order of the filament arrangement, reflected in the angle distribution under which the n -th nearest neighbour is located, is disregarded. The analysis of the angle distribution in this work was only made possible because of the automated measurement technique that was developed that allows a systematic analysis with high precision of a large number of images.

To generate statistically equivalent micro-structures, the fibre placement algorithm proposed by Vaughan and McCarthy [5] was further developed to utilise the presented data. In particular, the incorporation of the angle distribution of nearest neighbours guaranteed a statistically equivalent model. This also eliminated the jamming limit ($V_f \sim 0.70$) of this model generation approach. It is now possible to generate any V_f depending on the provided input data. The generated micro-structural models were validated with the same statistical descriptors as employed for the measurement of the filament distributions within fibre bundles.

In the future, the developed micro-structure generator will be used for the prediction of micro-mechanical properties of composites and analysis of reinforcement processing. For example, it will be possible to predict the micro-scale flow properties of statistical equivalent filament arrangements present within fibre bundles (Fig. 10). The results will then allow comparison with other generators of (artificial) micro-structures.

Fig. 10. Map of the flow velocity magnitude for transverse steady-state flow through a statistically equivalent micro-structure.

In addition, the measured change of the filament arrangement during deformation will be included in a compaction model for textile reinforcements. This will increase the understanding of fibre bundle deformation mechanism in textile reinforcements undergoing compaction during mould closure, e.g. explaining the effect of nesting and bundle deformation. The precise prediction of these phenomena will help to explain the influence of the bundle micro-structure on global component properties.

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